

Deep Learning-Based UWB-IMU Data Fusion for Indoor Positioning in Industrial Scenario

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ABSTRACT Accurate and precise wireless infrastructure-based positioning systems become crucial as industries move towards flexible, portable, and autonomous transportation systems such as Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs). Multipath-dominant dynamic environments like industries present significant challenges for wireless signal propagation and affect wireless positioning accuracy due to the interplay of reflected signals from obstacles. The achievable indoor positioning accuracy of the target AGV can be enhanced by fusing the measurements from the wireless infrastructure with the target's onboard sensor data. Nevertheless, the lack of correspondence between the wireless infrastructure and the target's onboard sensors causes the measurements from these two systems to arrive at irregular time steps. Using asynchronous measurements in the data fusion process can degrade the overall positioning accuracy of the target AGV. This paper proposes a novel deep learning-based data fusion approach to deal with asynchronous measurements from the wireless infrastructure Ultra-Wideband (UWB) and the target's onboard Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensor to achieve enhanced positioning accuracy of the target AGV. In particular, a two-stage cascaded Deep Neural Network (DNN) is proposed to deal with the asynchronized measurements from UWB and IMU sensors. The first stage of the DNN is used to obtain the initial position estimate of the AGV by processing the measurements from UWB. Subsequently, the second stage of the DNN fuses the initial position estimate of the AGV with the IMU sensor data to obtain the final enhanced position estimate. The proposed approach is validated with real-world experiments in an indoor industrial scenario using UWB technology in channel 2 (3.7–4.2 GHz) and an IMU sensor placed on an AGV. Moreover, the achievable positioning accuracy and the computational runtime to provide the position estimates with the proposed approach are analyzed. The experimental results show that the proposed approach achieves a mean absolute error of less than 10 cm, outperforming the considered baseline methods, Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM).

INDEX TERMS Autonomous transportation systems, data synchronization, deep neural networks, industries, inertial measurement units, ultra-wideband, wireless infrastructure-based positioning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless networks are becoming the central nervous system for industrial applications, enabling efficient communications and control of manufacturing processes [1]. Positioning

and/or tracking of industrial assets using wireless technologies is one such field of application in the industry that is investigated widely [2]. However, the complex layout of the industry with heavy metallic obstacles hinders wireless signal

propagation. Especially, the Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) and multipath phenomenon impede the interpretation of positional information from wireless signals, leading to inaccurate results [3]. Over the years, the focus has been dedicated to the accurate estimation of positional information like Time of Arrival (ToA) of Line-of-Sight (LoS) paths, which could be used in determining the User Equipment (UE) positions [4], [5], [6], [7], [8]. These works identify NLoS paths and eliminate the bias caused by the NLoS propagation. However, the efficiency of these approaches in a large-scale multipath dominant dynamic changing industrial environment is yet to be known. An alternative way of enhancing the accuracy of wireless positioning is to complement the radio signal measurements from the wireless infrastructure with the recorded data from UE onboard sensors through the data fusion technique.

A. PRIOR ART

1) MODEL-BASED DATA FUSION

The model-based approach follows a recursive mechanism to provide the position estimates by combining the motion model of a vehicle with the measurement model. The well-known algorithms under this category include Kalman Filters and their non-linear variants [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], Particle Filters [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], and Multi-Bernoulli Filters [23], [24]. The prior information of the vehicle is formulated in the form of a motion model, which is used to *predict* its initial position. On the other hand, the sensor's measurements are used to *update* the initial position. The fusion occurs in the *update* step by integrating measurements from multiple sensors [15]. In [9] and [14], information from the inertial sensors is fused with the range measurements of the wireless infrastructure using EKF to achieve a better position estimate of the user location. Enhancing the Ultra-Wideband (UWB) based positioning accuracy with inertial sensors in a mixed environment of LoS/NLoS scenarios and using a non-linear version of the Kalman Filter, UKF for data fusion was explored in [11] and [13] respectively. Authors in [12] proposed an EKF-based positioning approach by using the Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) measurements to predict the vehicle's state involving 2D position and the UWB measurements to update the vehicle's state. In [20], a cascaded positioning solution with UKF and Particle Filter was presented. To solve the problem of particle degeneracy in Particle Filters, authors in [22] proposed a Dynamic Feasible Region-based Particle Filter (DFRPF). The proposed method utilizes IMU measurements to predict the position of the person. The UWB anchors in LoS are identified with prior information, and the corresponding LoS range estimates are used to resample the particles.

The significant drawbacks of these approaches are their nature of handling non-linear measurements and assumptions about noise. The performance of EKF is limited in terms of linearizing the non-linear system through approximations. If the system is highly non-linear, similar to Automated Guided

Vehicle (AGV), with complex motion patterns in the industrial environments, it can lead to inaccurate results. Moreover, EKF assumes the noise model to be Gaussian. The noise affecting the sensor measurements in the complex multipath-dominant industrial environment might not constitute Gaussian. As a result, the performance of the EKF can degrade. On the other hand, the UKF requires well-defined state-space mathematical models for fusing measurements from multiple sensors, and using asynchronous measurements in the fusion could result in significant errors. In contrast to model-based approaches, data-driven approaches can capture non-linear relationships from input sensor data, learn to be robust to noisy data from training on noisy datasets, and be easily integrated with multiple sensors. Therefore, the dynamic behavior of indoor environments with obstacles exhibiting non-linear dynamics, the unpredictable non-Gaussian noise arising from the environmental factors, and the requirement for efficient data fusion approaches involving sensors with asynchronous measurements motivate the study of data-driven approaches.

2) DATA-DRIVEN BASED DATA FUSION

The role of data-driven approaches can be witnessed across various industrial applications, harnessing their capability to solve complex models and optimization problems [25], [26]. The advancements in machine learning inspired researchers to apply these approaches to achieve precise positioning in scenarios where traditional techniques do not work efficiently. The reasons favoring machine learning approaches for positioning include their ability to learn non-linear relationships directly through the training phase, fusing multimodal data through feature extraction layers, and implementing a model-free positioning system [15]. Different techniques, including supervised, self-supervised, and unsupervised learning, have been used to fuse the measurements from multiple sensors and achieve precise positioning. Using supervised learning, authors in [27] implemented a positioning solution by fusing the Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) signal strength measurements with the inertial sensors of a mobile phone using neural networks. The ability of the neural network to model the non-linear relationship was used to correct the non-linear approximation errors of EKF. In [28], authors proposed a two-stage localization framework consisting of coarse localization and refined localization modules. The smartphone's Long-Term Evolution (LTE) signal draws a region of the user's possible initial location. Thereby, the WiFi signals and camera images are fused through neural networks to estimate the final position of the user. The work in [29] utilized visual, IMU, and UWB sensors for positioning and proposed a DNN-based data fusion solution (VIU-Net) to achieve enhanced positioning results. Positioning with UWB ToA measurements using deep learning techniques, including the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), are considered to achieve better positioning accuracy in [30] and [31] respectively. Techniques to generate ground truth labels directly from the input data with self-supervised

learning were also explored in the literature. In [32], the motion features of a vehicle extracted from the camera and IMU sensors are fused with Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to predict the vehicle position. The augmented views of the camera images and IMU readings are used to generate pseudo labels, which are used to train the model. Fusing the visual and inertial measurements using DNNs to achieve precise positioning with an unsupervised learning approach was presented in [33].

B. LIMITATIONS OF PRIOR ART

The works in the prior art considered multimodal sensors, which provide distinct measurements at different output frequencies or sampling rates (we stick to the word sampling rates for the rest of the paper). As a result, there is no time correspondence between the sensor measurements, leading to data synchronization issues. In addition, data from the sensors might not arrive simultaneously due to different sampling rates, especially for wireless measurements, which can be affected by environmental factors. In such cases, using asynchronous measurements in the data fusion process can lead to inaccurate positioning results. However, despite its relevance in real-world scenarios, less emphasis has been placed on multimodal data fusion with asynchronous measurements and its impact on positioning accuracy. For instance, industries operate AGVs with multimodal sensors from different manufacturers. These sensors do not operate at the same sampling rates. Therefore, the industrial application that uses the sensory data from AGVs needs to work with the existing setup, avoiding adjusting the sampling rate of each sensor.

C. NOVELTY AND CONTRIBUTIONS

In this paper, we improve the mobile target's achievable wireless infrastructure-based indoor positioning accuracy through a data fusion approach and demonstrate the results through real-world experiments. To this end, we present a detailed investigation into the application of DNNs as a powerful tool for fusing measurements from the wireless infrastructure and the mobile target's onboard sensors to achieve enhanced position estimates of the target. The key questions related to DNN-based multimodal data fusion for indoor positioning are: (i) How to provide position estimations with the DNNs, relying on the fact that different sensors generate data at various sampling rates and manually adjusting the output sampling rate of each sensor is not possible in the real-world scenario? (ii) What performance gain in positioning accuracy can be achieved with DNN-based data fusion compared to a conventional model-based approach such as EKF and a data-driven approach such as LSTM?

This paper answers the questions mentioned above by demonstrating the efficiency of DNN-based data fusion using UWB and IMU measurements, with an AGV being the target UE to be positioned. The key contributions of this work are outlined below.

- 1) We propose a novel and efficient data fusion solution for the measurements between the wireless infrastructure

and the UE sensor technology. Opposed to the works of prior art, which rely on a model-based approach for data fusion [12] and assume the underlying system dynamics to be partially known [34], our proposed data-driven DNN-based data fusion solution learns the system dynamics from the input measurements. Moreover, our approach can fuse the measurements without manually adjusting the output sampling rate of each source of measurement. We implement our proposed data fusion solution on the application of indoor positioning to enhance the positioning accuracy of an AGV.

- 2) In addition to the DNN-based data fusion solution, we propose and implement two other solutions based on EKF and LSTM approaches. We validate the performance of our proposed data fusion and positioning approaches in terms of achievable positioning accuracy and the computational runtime for providing position estimates through real-world experiments in the industrial environment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the system model, including the details of the wireless infrastructure and the UE sensor technology under consideration. The problem under investigation is elaborated in Section III. The proposed DNN-based multimodal data fusion and positioning solution to the problem is presented in Section IV. In Section V, we analyze the positioning accuracy achieved with our proposed solution compared to the benchmarks considered. The significant learnings are summarized in Section VI. Lastly, Section VII concludes the work with a few recommendations for future research.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this work, we consider the UWB system as a wireless infrastructure with a set of nodes. Each of the nodes is configured either as an anchor or tag. The anchors are deployed in the Area of Interest (AoI) for performing positioning with known position coordinates $\{p_{ac} = (p_{x_{ac}}, p_{y_{ac}}), p_{ac} \in \mathbb{R}^2, ac \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}\}$, with M being the maximum number of anchors, which is six. On the other hand, the tag is connected to the target AGV, whose position needs to be determined $\{p_{tag} = (p_{x_{tag}}, p_{y_{tag}}), p_{tag} \in \mathbb{R}^2\}$. Each of the nodes in the UWB network is provided with a scheduled time interval to transmit or receive messages to/from neighboring nodes. The scheduling is done using the Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) scheme consisting of beacons sent at periodic intervals and frames with duration τ as shown in Fig. 1. The beacons are sent by the master anchor periodically at an interval of T_s to synchronize other anchors in the network. The time duration between two beacons defines a superframe. Furthermore, the superframe comprises K TDMA frames. As shown in Fig. 1, each TDMA frame contains a broadcast slot, allowing the tag to broadcast a message, followed by the response slots for receiving messages from the M anchors. It is to be noted that the master anchor allocates each response slot to a single anchor. In this work, only one tag is used, and the tag is provided with a fixed slot to broadcast

FIGURE 1. Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA) scheduling in Ultra-Wideband (UWB) network.

the message in a repeated TDMA frame cycle. Providing more slots to the tag in a repeated TDMA cycle is possible. However, a single slot per tag in a repeated TDMA cycle was used in this work to ensure a controlled and interference-free environment, i.e., minimizing the likelihood of interference with other devices operating in the same frequency range of UWB. At the end of each TDMA frame, the tag obtains M responses with messages corresponding to each anchor in the UWB network. As the tag knows the start time of each response slot and the anchor to which it is allotted, upon receiving messages from M anchors, the M Times-of-Flight (ToF) are computed by the tag. The M ToFs are, in turn, used to estimate M distances using Single-Sided Two-Way Ranging (SS-TWR) as mentioned in [35], [36]. The distances obtained by the tag are relatively in 3D due to differences in the heights of the deployed anchors and the tag. As the focus of our work is 2D positioning, the obtained 3D distances need to be transformed to 2D as $d_{2D} = ((d_{3D})^2 - (\Delta h)^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, where Δh represents the difference in heights between the anchors and tag. We consider 2D positioning in this work because the mobile target AGV operates only in 2D space, requiring position estimates to be obtained in 2D. Moreover, the ground truth sensor, LiDAR, is designed to provide position estimates in 2D, making 3D positioning validation difficult.

For UE sensor technology, we use the IMU sensor, which consists of an accelerometer and a gyroscope and their corresponding measurements. It is to be noted that the IMU sensor has a specific coordinate frame called the local frame, and it moves following the movement of the AGV to which it is attached. On the other hand, the position coordinates of the deployed UWB anchors define the global coordinate frame of the AoI, which is fixed and does not change with the AGV's movement. We use the global coordinates as the frame of reference for positioning. The measurements provided by the IMU sensor correspond to the local coordinate frame, which needs to be mapped to a global coordinate frame using a rotation matrix given by

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\Psi) & \cos(\Psi) - \sin(\Psi) & \cos(\Psi) + \sin(\Psi) \\ \sin(\Psi) & \sin(\Psi) - \cos(\Psi) & \sin(\Psi) + \cos(\Psi) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where Ψ denotes the yaw angle, which is obtained by integrating the z -axis angular velocity from the gyroscope over time. Specifically, the yaw angle at time step t is computed as

$$\Psi_t = \Psi_{t-1} + \omega_{z_t} \cdot \Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where Ψ_{t-1} indicates the yaw angle at the previous time step, ω_{z_t} represents the angular velocity along z -axis at time step t from the gyroscope, and Δt refers to the sampling period. It is to be noted that the yaw angle at the initial time step is already known in advance. On the other hand, the influence of gravity imposed on the acceleration measurements in the x and y axes needs to be removed. To do so, the gravity in the global coordinate frame $g_G = [0, 0, -9.8]^T$ is transformed to the local frame by

$$g_L = R^{-1} \cdot g_G. \quad (3)$$

Thereafter, the effect of gravity is removed from the accelerometer measurements by

$$a_{\text{corrected}} = a_{\text{measured}} - g_L, \quad (4)$$

where a_{measured} corresponds to the actual measurements recorded by the accelerometer in the local coordinate frame. Lastly, the corrected accelerometer measurements are transformed to the global coordinate frame by

$$a_G = R \cdot a_{\text{corrected}} \quad (5)$$

where $a_G = [a_x, a_y, a_z]^T$ indicates the acceleration measurements in the global coordinate frame. The IMU anomalies, such as accelerometer bias and gyroscope drift, can still be evident in the IMU measurements. However, the proposed deep learning-based positioning approach can learn the IMU anomalies from the input data. To maximize the fusion performance of our algorithm, we translate the global accelerations into the distance traversed by AGV as $d_{\text{imu}} = v\Delta t + \frac{1}{2}a(\Delta t)^2$, where v and Δt refers to the velocity and the time interval between IMU measurements, which are known parameters. The term a indicates the total acceleration given by $a = ((a_{x_G})^2 + (a_{y_G})^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The choice of using d_{imu} comes from the fact that adding raw accelerations and orientation information from the IMU sensor as input to the DNN does not enhance the positioning performance. The acceleration measurements recorded by the IMU sensor remain constant if the AGV does not change its velocity during its movement along a trajectory. Moreover, the orientation measurements recorded by the IMU sensor also remain constant if the AGV does not make turns while moving along a trajectory. In our specific industrial environment, the AGV maintains constant movement (most of the time in a given trajectory) with minimal variations in acceleration and taking turns. In such cases, adding raw IMU sensor data as input does not help the DNN to learn to provide the position estimates as the output. Therefore, to have a reliable input feature through which the DNN can learn, we translate the measurements from the IMU sensor to a new measurement d_{imu} and feed it as input to the DNN.

The UWB tag provides the measurements at an output sampling rate of 10 Hz approximately. On the other hand, the

FIGURE 2. Deep Neural Network (DNN) based multimodal data fusion architecture for indoor positioning.

measurements from the IMU sensor are obtained at a much higher output sampling rate, i.e., 50 Hz. The measurements from these two systems are not obtained at the same timestamps, leading to asynchrony and temporal misalignment of the measurements. Integrating asynchronous measurements in the data fusion and position estimation process can impact the achievable positioning accuracy of the target.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

We consider an AGV equipped with three different sensors $S \in \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$: UWB tag, IMU, and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR), which provide measurements at different sampling rates. The measurements from the sensors are represented by $\Omega^{(S)} = \{\Omega_1^{(S)}, \Omega_2^{(S)}, \dots, \Omega_N^{(S)}\}$, where $\Omega_i^{(S)}$ represents the measurement from the sensors S at i -th time, with N being the maximum. The measurement is defined by $\Omega_i^{(S)} = \{t, \mathbf{x}\}$, where t is the timestamp of the measurement and \mathbf{x} is the state vector. For the UWB tag, the state vector includes the 2D distances obtained through SS-TWR between the UWB tag and a total of M UWB anchors $\mathbf{x}_{\text{tag}} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_M]^T$. For the IMU sensor, the state vector includes accelerations from the accelerometer and angular velocities from gyroscope $\mathbf{x}_{\text{imu}} = [a_x, a_y, a_z, g_x, g_y, g_z]^T$. Lastly, the state vector for LiDAR includes the position coordinates of the AGV $\mathbf{x}_{\text{lidar}} = [p_x, p_y]^T$, which is used as a ground truth. The LiDAR sensor provides position estimates of the AGV as the output using the LiDAR-Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithm [37]. The problem of interest is given the measurements $\Omega^{(S)}$ at discrete times $\{t_i\}_{i=1}^N$ with asynchronized samples from UWB and IMU sensors, how to fuse the measurements from both sensors to provide the position estimations of AGV over a continuous trajectory? We formulate this as

$$\{\Omega_i^{(S)}, t_i\}_{i=1}^N \rightarrow \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N, \quad (6)$$

where $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N = [\hat{p}_x, \hat{p}_y]^T$ represents the estimated position of the AGV in 2D coordinates at time t_i .

IV. DEEP LEARNING-BASED MULTIMODAL DATA FUSION

The architecture for enhancing the indoor positioning accuracy of the AGV by fusing the measurements from UWB and IMU sensors using DNNs is illustrated in Fig. 2. In the subsequent sections, we go through Fig. 2, introducing the steps involved in the data fusion process and procedures for training.

A. DEEP CASCADED POSITIONING

The DNNs are the specialized architectures in deep learning with multiple layers of neurons, allowing the network to learn complex data representations. The proposed deep-learning-based data fusion and positioning solution uses two DNNs cascaded together, allowing the information to flow from the first DNN to the second DNN. This architecture is motivated by the industrial requirement to have a high positioning update rate of the AGV and solve the problem of fusing measurements from sensors with different sampling rates. In addition, the cascaded DNNs offer modularity, flexibility, and performance benefits. (i) The complex problem can be split into subproblems, focusing on learning positional features from each sensor and their respective measurements. (ii) Offering plug-and-play design, allowing modification of the parameters of one of the DNNs without affecting the overall architecture. (iii) The architecture enables progressive refinement, where the coarse output produced by the first DNN can be refined in the second DNN to improve the precision.

First stage of DNN: The first stage of the DNN is used to process the measurements from the UWB network. We use the distances (2D) computed by the tag to the M anchors in the AoI using SS-TWR as inputs. Moreover, to

enable the network to learn the temporal dependencies, we also add the previous position of the AGV in x and y coordinates as additional inputs to the first DNN. To this end, the input vector to the first DNN (D1) at time t comprises $\mathbf{x}_t^{\text{D1}} = [p_{x_{t-1}}, p_{y_{t-1}}, d_1, \dots, d_M]^T$ as shown in Fig. 2. The first DNN is trained to estimate the initial position of the AGV. The ground truth positions of the AGV obtained from the LiDAR sensor are used for supervised learning during the training procedure. Each neuron in the layer l implements an activation function to introduce non-linearity and learn complex patterns. In particular, if \mathbf{x}_t^{rs} defines the input vector for the r -th neuron in s -th hidden layer, then the output for the respective neuron is interpreted as $y_{rs} = f_{rs}(\mathbf{w}_{rs}^T \mathbf{x}_t^{rs} + b_{rs})$, where \mathbf{w}_{rs} and b_{rs} indicates weights and bias associated with the neuron. The activation function is represented by $f_{rs}(\cdot)$. The input vector is passed through all the hidden layers to provide the initial position of the AGV $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{initial}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{initial}}]^T$ as the output of the first DNN, illustrated in Fig. 2.

Second stage of DNN: The second DNN is used to fuse the measurements from the UWB and IMU sensors. The second DNN takes the estimated position of the AGV in x and y coordinates as well as the measurement conveying the distance traversed by the AGV d_{imu} , computed from the IMU measurements (discussed in Section II) as the inputs. To this end, the input vector to the second DNN (D2) comprises $\mathbf{x}_t^{\text{D2}} = [\hat{p}_x, \hat{p}_y, d_{\text{imu}}]^T$. The second DNN is trained to estimate the final position of the AGV, which is the result of the data fusion. The selected inputs can contribute to DNN learning in reliable trajectory estimation even when the trajectories are not straight (e.g., circular trajectories). Since the accelerations in the local coordinate frame from the IMU sensor are transformed into the global coordinate frame using the yaw angle, it helps correctly align the AGV's movement in the global coordinate frame. The transformed accelerations in the global coordinate frame are then used to compute d_{imu} . Therefore, the sequences of distances obtained over multiple time steps give insights into the motion of the AGV in a circular trajectory. The ground truth positions of the AGV obtained from the LiDAR sensor are used for supervised learning during the training procedure. The activation function $f_{rs}(\cdot)$ captures the non-linear dependencies. Thereafter, the input vector is passed through all the hidden layers to provide the final position of the AGV $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{final}}]^T$ as the output of the second DNN, depicted in Fig. 2.

Cascading the DNNs: The first and second DNNs are cascaded through a gate, which controls the flow of information to the second DNN as shown in Fig. 2. It is important to recall that the IMU sensor provides more output measurements per time unit (50 Hz) than the UWB tag (approx. 10 Hz). Therefore, the key idea is that whenever the measurement from the UWB tag is available, we fuse it with the IMU measurement to enhance the position estimation of the AGV. In those time instances when the measurement from the UWB tag is not available, we rely on the IMU to estimate the position of the AGV. For example, let's assume that at the current time step t , we obtain the measurement from the UWB

Algorithm 1: Proposed Algorithm for the Problem (6).

Training phase:

- 1 Acquire measurement data from the sensors $\Omega^{(S)}$, $S \in \{s_1, s_2\}$ through a measurement campaign.
- 2 Translate global accelerations from the IMU sensor to the distance traversed by AGV d_{imu} .
- 3 Train both the DNNs with the position estimates created by the LiDAR measurements as ground truth and determine a model with minimal training loss to provide the position estimations of AGV $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$.
- 4 Store the models.

Testing phase :

- 5 **for** $i \geq 1$ **do**
- 6 Acquire measurement data from the sensors $\Omega^{(S)}$, $S \in \{s_1, s_2\}$ for the current time step t_i .
- 7 **if** UWB data is available at t_i **then**
- 8 Provide $[p_{x_{t_i-1}}, p_{y_{t_i-1}}, d_1, \dots, d_M]^T$ as inputs to the first DNN.
- 9 Determine AGV's initial position $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{initial}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{initial}}]^T$.
- 10 Provide $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{initial}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{initial}}]^T$ and d_{imu} as inputs to the second DNN.
- 11 **else**
- 12 Provide $[\hat{p}_{x_{t_i-1}}^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_{y_{t_i-1}}^{\text{final}}]^T$ and d_{imu} as inputs to the second DNN.
- 13 **end if**
- 14 **end for**
- 15 **return** $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N = [\hat{p}_x^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{final}}]^T$

tag $\Omega_t^{(s_1)}$. This measurement corresponds to distances to a set of M anchors, which are given to the first DNN along with the previous position of the AGV as inputs. Based on its learning experience, the first DNN estimates the initial position of the AGV $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{initial}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{initial}}]^T$ for the current time step t . Thereafter, the initial estimated position is given as input to the second DNN along with the IMU measurement $\Omega_t^{(s_2)}$, i.e., distance traversed by the AGV d_{imu} . Subsequently, the second DNN provides the final estimated position of the AGV $[\hat{p}_x^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{final}}]^T$. However, at the current time step t , if the measurement from the UWB tag is unavailable, the first DNN becomes inactive, and only the second DNN is used for the AGV position estimation. Nonetheless, the second DNN requires the position of AGV as one of the inputs. Thus, the final position estimated by the cascaded DNNs during the previous time step $t-1$, $[\hat{p}_{x_{t-1}}^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_{y_{t-1}}^{\text{final}}]^T$ is used as the input to the second DNN along with d_{imu} . The entire process is summarized in Algorithm 1. To this end, the gate is used to select the latest available position of AGV, which can be from the first DNN or the cascaded DNNs (from the previous time step $t-1$), and provide it as input to the second DNN according to the following condition.

$$(\hat{p}_x, \hat{p}_y) = \begin{cases} (\hat{p}_x^{\text{initial}}, \hat{p}_y^{\text{initial}}), & \text{if UWB data is available,} \\ (\hat{p}_{x_{t-1}}^{\text{final}}, \hat{p}_{y_{t-1}}^{\text{final}}), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

B. TRAINING PROCEDURE

We consider an offline training procedure described in Algorithm 1, where the data required for training the cascaded DNNs are collected beforehand through a measurement campaign. The key steps in the training procedure include data collection and model training.

FIGURE 3. Run 1—Training trajectory of the Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) for data collection. In addition, the figure shows the surrounding objects detected by the Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensor onboard the AGV.

1) DATA COLLECTION

The UWB anchors are installed in the AoI for positioning, and the UWB tag is connected to the AGV. In addition, the AGV is also equipped with IMU and LiDAR sensors, is controlled by Robot Operating System 2 (ROS2), and is provided with a pre-defined trajectory to traverse in the given AoI as shown in Fig. 3. As the AGV follows the training route, the UWB tag, IMU, and LiDAR sensors collect their respective measurements and are logged into the AGV’s control computer. Subsequently, the IMU measurements are translated into d_{imu} as described in Section II. It is to be noted that the training data also involves asynchronous measurements from the UWB and IMU sensors. The measurements are divided into training (80%) and validation sets (20%).

2) MODEL TRAINING

The measurements collected by the AGV along the training trajectory are used to train each of the DNNs separately. The inputs to the first DNN include the previous position of the AGV and distances from the AGV to M anchors. The LiDAR position estimates are used as the ground truth labels. We adopt the Mean Square Error (MSE) as the loss function, which is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}^{MSE}(\Theta) = \mathbb{E}\{\|\mathbf{p} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}\|_2^2\}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{p} is the vector containing the ground truth position of AGV in x and y directions. The estimated position is $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$. The trainable parameters containing weights and biases of the neural network are represented by Θ . The deep learning model is implemented in Python with the Keras framework, which consists of five layers with $\{8, 128, 64, 32, 2\}$ neurons per layer. The Rectification Linear Unit (ReLU) function is used as the activation function, and Adaptive Moment Estimation (ADAM) is used as the optimizer with a learning rate of 10^{-3} . The DNN is trained with a batch size of 32 for 100 epochs. The number of layers, neurons per layer, batch size, and epochs are decided based on experimentation. The second DNN takes the estimated position of AGV and the distance traversed by AGV as inputs. The LiDAR position estimates

FIGURE 4. AGV mounted with UWB, Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), and LiDAR sensors (left). The considered industrial scenario (right).

are used as ground truth labels with MSE as the loss function defined as

$$\mathcal{L}^{MSE}(\Theta) = \mathbb{E}\{\|\mathbf{p} - \hat{\mathbf{p}}\|_2^2\}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ is the vector containing the estimated position of AGV, which is the result of the data fusion. The DNN comprises five layers with $\{3, 128, 64, 32, 2\}$ neurons per layer. All the training settings remain the same as that of the first DNN.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents the results of our analysis of the positioning performance. First, we describe the experimental setup used in the study. Next, we consider and provide details on fusing measurements with two benchmarks: EKF [12] and LSTM. Lastly, we compare the achievable positioning accuracy of AGV using our proposed solution against the benchmarks.

A. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this study, we have used the ActiveShuttle from Bosch Rexroth as the test AGV [2]. The AGV is controlled by an onboard computer with ROS2 and is equipped with UWB tag, IMU, and LiDAR sensors, as shown in Fig. 4. The UWB tag employed is Qorvo DWM1001C, which works in channel 2 with a center frequency of 3.9 GHz and a bandwidth of 500 MHz. The IMU sensor corresponds to STMicroelectronics LSM6DS3, featuring a 3-axis digital accelerometer and a 3-axis digital gyroscope. The safety laser LiDAR scanner on the AGV is used to obtain the ground truth data, i.e., position estimates of the AGV. The LiDAR uses the LiDAR-SLAM algorithm to provide the position estimates of the AGV [37]. A detailed description of the LiDAR-SLAM algorithm is beyond the scope of this paper. The experimental AoI corresponds to an industrial scenario with dimensions of $9\text{ m} \times 12\text{ m} \times 3.3\text{ m}$ approximately. A concrete wall, metal cupboards, metal tables, plastic containers, and other robots are present around the AoI. Six UWB anchors were deployed around the AoI on the aluminum frame at a height of 2 m. The UWB tag is installed on the AGV at a height of 1 m from the ground level.

Algorithm 2: Extended Kalman Filter Algorithm.

Input:
IMU accelerations: $[a_x, a_y]_G^T$;
UWB anchor coordinates: $\{(p_{x_{ac}}, p_{y_{ac}})\}$, $ac \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ };
UWB SS-TWR distances: $[d_1, d_2, \dots, d_M]^T$;
Process noise covariance \mathbf{C}_x ;
Measurement noise covariance \mathbf{C}_r ;
State covariance $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_t$.
Output: $\mathbf{x} = [p_x, p_y, v_x, v_y]^T$

```

1 Define the state vector  $\mathbf{x}$ .
2 for  $i \geq 1$  do
3   if UWB data is available at time  $t_i$  then
4     Predict
5     Compute state transition  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{w}_t$  using IMU
      accelerations at time  $t_i + 1$  as control inputs.
6     Compute state covariance  $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1} = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i}\mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{C}_x$ .
7
8     Update
9     Use  $[d_1, \dots, d_M]^T$  in the observation vector  $\mathbf{z}_{t_i+1}$ .
10    Compute Jacobian  $\mathbf{H}_{t_i+1} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1}}$ .
11    Compute Residual  $\mathbf{v}_{t_i+1} = \mathbf{z}_{t_i+1} - \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1})$ .
12    Compute Kalman gain
13     $\mathbf{K}_{t_i+1} = \hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1}\mathbf{H}_{t_i+1}^T(\mathbf{H}_{t_i+1}\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1}\mathbf{H}_{t_i+1}^T + \mathbf{C}_r)^{-1}$ .
14    Update the state vector
15     $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1}^* = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1} + \mathbf{K}_{t_i+1}(\mathbf{v}_{t_i+1} - \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1}))$ .
16    Update state covariance  $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1}^* = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{t_i+1}\mathbf{H}_{t_i+1})\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1}$ .
17  else
18    Predict
19    Compute state transition  $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t_i+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{w}_t$  using IMU
      accelerations at time  $t_i + 1$  as control inputs.
20    Compute state covariance  $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i+1} = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t_i}\mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{C}_x$ .
21  end if
22 end for

```

B. BENCHMARKS

In this study, we validate the performance of our proposed data fusion and positioning solution against the following benchmarks.

1) EXTENDED KALMAN FILTER

We use the approach in [12] to fuse the UWB and IMU measurements. In the prediction step of EKF, we rely on the IMU measurements to estimate the position of AGV. In particular, the accelerations in the global coordinate frame $[a_x, a_y]_G^T$ from the IMU are used to predict the AGV's position, following the motion model. In the update step of EKF, we use the UWB measurements to correct and compute the position of AGV. To this end, the state vector of the AGV includes its position and velocity in x and y directions at time t , $\mathbf{x}_t = [p_x, p_y, v_x, v_y]^T$. The IMU accelerations are used as control inputs to predict the new state or future state of the AGV $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1}$, following the state transition equation $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_t + \mathbf{w}_t$, where the state transition matrix \mathbf{A} , the control input matrix \mathbf{B} , and the control input vector \mathbf{u}_t are given as

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \\ \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta t \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{u}_t = \begin{bmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \end{bmatrix}_G, \quad (10)$$

where Δt is the interval between two consecutive IMU measurements. In addition, the process noise $\mathbf{w}_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ is assumed to be Gaussian with mean μ and variance σ^2 .

Thereafter, the error in the state prediction known as state covariance is computed as $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t+1} = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_t\mathbf{A}^T + \mathbf{C}_x$, with \mathbf{C}_x being the process noise covariance representing uncertainties in IMU readings. The \mathbf{C}_x is parameterized as

$$\mathbf{C}_x = \mathbf{C}_{\text{motion}} + \mathbf{C}_w, \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{\text{motion}}$ and \mathbf{C}_w represents the noise due to uncertainties in IMU measurements and process noise \mathbf{w}_t , given as

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{motion}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t^4}{4}\sigma_{a_x}^2 & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2}\sigma_{a_x}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta t^4}{4}\sigma_{a_y}^2 & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2}\sigma_{a_y}^2 \\ \frac{\Delta t^3}{2}\sigma_{a_x}^2 & 0 & \Delta t^2\sigma_{a_x}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2}\sigma_{a_y}^2 & 0 & \Delta t^2\sigma_{a_y}^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where $\sigma_{a_x}^2$ and $\sigma_{a_y}^2$ represents the variance of IMU acceleration noise in x and y , respectively.

$$\mathbf{C}_w = \text{diag}(\sigma_{p_x}^2, \sigma_{p_y}^2, \sigma_{v_x}^2, \sigma_{v_y}^2), \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma_{p_x}^2$ and $\sigma_{p_y}^2$ describes position noise variance in x and y , respectively. Furthermore, $\sigma_{v_x}^2$ and $\sigma_{v_y}^2$ indicates velocity noise variance in x and y , respectively. The UWB measurements are used to update the state vector. In particular, the distances computed by the tag to each of the M anchors are used in the observation vector \mathbf{z}_{t+1} . The distance to anchor M can be mathematically represented as $d_M = ((p_x - p_{x_M})^2 + (p_y - p_{y_M})^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, where (p_x, p_y) indicates the position of the AGV and (p_{x_M}, p_{y_M}) represents the known position of the anchor M . The EKF computes residual $\mathbf{v}_{t+1} = \mathbf{z}_{t+1} - \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1})$, representing the difference between the observation vector \mathbf{z}_{t+1} and the predicted measurements at time $t + 1$, $\mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1})$. To obtain the predicted measurements, the observation vector needs to be linearized around the state vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1}$. To do this, the Jacobian \mathbf{H}_{t+1} is computed as

$$\mathbf{H}_{t+1} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p_x - p_{x_1}}{d_1} & \frac{p_y - p_{y_1}}{d_1} & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{p_x - p_{x_M}}{d_M} & \frac{p_y - p_{y_M}}{d_M} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

Subsequently, the state is updated as $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1}^* = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} + \mathbf{K}_{t+1}(\mathbf{z}_{t+1} - \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1}))$, where $\mathbf{K}_{t+1} = \hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t+1}\mathbf{H}_{t+1}^T(\mathbf{H}_{t+1}\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t+1}\mathbf{H}_{t+1}^T + \mathbf{C}_r)^{-1}$ is the Kalman gain and \mathbf{C}_r is the measurement noise covariance representing the uncertainty in the UWB measurements. The \mathbf{C}_r is a diagonal matrix, representing the uncertainty in UWB distance measurement to each anchor and is given by

$$\mathbf{C}_r = \text{diag}(\sigma_1^2, \sigma_2^2, \dots, \sigma_M^2) \quad (15)$$

Lastly, the error in the state estimation is also updated as $\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t+1}^* = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_{t+1}\mathbf{H}_{t+1})\hat{\mathbf{\Upsilon}}_{t+1}$. The entire process is summarized in Algorithm 2.

2) LONG SHORT-TERM MEMORY

The second benchmark considered in this work is LSTM. We use an approach similar to the cascaded DNNs (discussed

Algorithm 3: Long Short-Term Memory Algorithm.

Training phase:

- 1 Acquire measurement data from the sensors $\Omega^{(S)}$, $S \in \{s_1, s_2\}$ through a measurement campaign.
- 2 Translate global accelerations from the IMU sensor to the distance traversed by AGV d_{imu} .
- 3 Set data sequence length to be 2.
- 4 Train both the LSTM networks with the position estimates created by the LiDAR measurements as ground truth and determine a model with minimal training loss to provide the position estimations of AGV $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$.
- 5 Store the models.

Testing phase :

- 6 **for** $i \geq 1$ **do**
- 7 Acquire measurement data from the sensors $\Omega^{(S)}$, $S \in \{s_1, s_2\}$ for the current time step t_i .
- 8 **if** UWB data is available at t_i **then**
- 9 Provide $[d_1, \dots, d_M]^T$ as inputs to the first LSTM network.
- 10 Determine AGV's initial position $[\hat{p}_x^{initial}, \hat{p}_y^{initial}]^T$.
- 11 Provide $[\hat{p}_x^{initial}, \hat{p}_y^{initial}]^T$ and d_{imu} as inputs to the second LSTM network.
- 12 **else**
- 13 Provide $[\hat{p}_x^{final}_{t_i-1}, \hat{p}_y^{final}_{t_i-1}]^T$ and d_{imu} as inputs to the second LSTM network.
- 14 **end if**
- 15 **end for**
- 16 **return** $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N = [\hat{p}_x^{final}, \hat{p}_y^{final}]^T$

in Section IV) for fusing UWB and IMU measurements. To this end, a two-stage cascaded LSTM is used to estimate the position of the AGV. The first stage of the LSTM network is used to map the inputs of UWB SS-TWR distances to the initial position of the AGV. After that, the second LSTM network is used to fuse AGV's initial position with the IMU measurements to obtain the enhanced position estimation of the AGV.

The first stage of the LSTM (LS1) network consists of four layers, including one input layer, two LSTM layers, and one dense layer. The input layer takes UWB SS-TWR distances computed by the tag to M anchors $\mathbf{x}_t^{LS1} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_M]^T$ at timestep t as the inputs. The inputs to the LSTM are provided in the form of structured data sequences. Each data sequence contains measurements corresponding to different timestamps. In this work, we consider the data sequence length of 2, representing the LSTM layer that takes 2 consecutive time steps of input measurements to provide the output. For instance, the first data sequence contains $\text{seq}_1 = [\mathbf{x}_{t_1}, \mathbf{x}_{t_2}]^T$ as the input measurements for timesteps t_1 and t_2 , fed to the first stage of the LSTM network. Consequently, the initial estimated position of the AGV is obtained as the output. Next, the second data sequence contains $\text{seq}_2 = [\mathbf{x}_{t_3}, \mathbf{x}_{t_4}]^T$ as the input measurements, fed to the first stage of the LSTM network to obtain the initial position estimate. The cycle continues till all the data sequences have been processed. The structure of the LSTM layer is shown in Fig. 5, which provides the cell state \mathbf{cs}_t and the hidden state \mathbf{hs}_t as the outputs. The cell state \mathbf{cs}_t represents the long-term of the LSTM network. Specifically, it monitors the input measurements at each timestep and updates its memory by removing irrelevant information or adding relevant information. In short, the cell state holds the cumulative information from the data sequence. On the other hand, the hidden state \mathbf{hs}_t represents the

FIGURE 5. The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cell structure with forget, input, and output gates.

short-term memory of the LSTM network. It holds the information corresponding to the current timestep, which is necessary to generate the current output. Three gates, the forget gate, input gate, and output gate, have been used in the LSTM network to enable the network to control the information flow. The forget gate takes the input \mathbf{x}_{t_1} and decides how much of the information has to be retained by computing

$$f_{t_1} = \sigma(\mathbf{w}_f^T \mathbf{x}_{t_1} + b_f), \quad (16)$$

where σ is the ReLU activation function, \mathbf{w}_f and b_f are the weights and bias of the forget gate. The input gate decides how much of the information from the input \mathbf{x}_{t_1} has to be added to the cell state by computing

$$i_{t_1} = \sigma(\mathbf{w}_i^T \mathbf{x}_{t_1} + b_i), \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{w}_i and b_i are the weights and bias of the input gate. Subsequently, the cell state \mathbf{cs}_t is updated based on the previous cell state \mathbf{cs}_{t_0} and the input gate i_{t_1} as

$$\mathbf{cs}_{t_1} = f_{t_1} \mathbf{cs}_{t_0} + i_{t_1} \tilde{\mathbf{cs}}_{t_1}, \quad (18)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{cs}}_{t_1} = \tanh(\mathbf{w}_{cs}^T \mathbf{x}_{t_1} + b_{cs}), \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{cs}}_{t_1}$ is the input to the cell state. Finally, the output gate o_{t_1} and the hidden state \mathbf{hs}_{t_1} are computed as

$$o_{t_1} = \sigma(\mathbf{w}_o^T \mathbf{x}_{t_1} + b_o), \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{hs}_{t_1} = o_{t_1} \tanh(\mathbf{cs}_{t_1}). \quad (21)$$

Therefore, the hidden state holds the initial position estimate of the AGV, which is given as input to the second stage of the LSTM. In particular, the second stage of the LSTM also contains one input layer, two LSTM layers, and one dense layer with the same processing steps as the first LSTM. However, the inputs to the second stage of the LSTM (LS2) network are $\mathbf{x}_t^{LS2} = [\hat{p}_x^{initial}, \hat{p}_y^{initial}, d_{imu}]^T$ with a data sequence length of 2. In addition, similar to the cascaded DNNs, the gate is used to select the latest available position of the AGV as input to the second stage of LSTM based on (7). The data collected during the measurement campaign is divided into training (80%) and validation (20%) datasets. The LSTM model is implemented in Python, and MSE is used as the loss function. The entire procedure is summarized in Algorithm 3.

FIGURE 6. Comparison of Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), LSTM, and DNN-based data fusion and positioning approaches for Run 1 trajectory.

TABLE 1. Comparison of Achievable Positioning Accuracy for Different Trajectories of AGV Using EKF, LSTM, and DNN in Centimeters (cm)

Metric	Positioning solution	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
Mean Absolute Error	EKF	21.0	22.8	15.5
	Cascaded LSTM	10.1	14.2	10.0
	Cascaded DNN	5.3	7.6	6.5
90-th percentile	EKF	27.5	30	25.8
	Cascaded LSTM	21.8	23	19.8
	Cascaded DNN	15	18	16.2

C. POSITIONING RESULTS

The data-driven positioning algorithms discussed in this work are trained offline. These algorithms must attain acceptable performance in positioning the AGV during the testing phase when they are provided with data different from the training procedure. To this end, we evaluate the positioning performance of both data-driven and model-based approaches on three distinct trajectories of the AGV in the given AoI. The first trajectory corresponds to the route used by the AGV during the training procedure to collect the data required for training the data-driven approaches. We refer to this trajectory as Run 1. We also evaluate the positioning performance of the investigated algorithms on trajectories Run 2 and Run 3, which are unseen and new to the AGV. Table 1 shows the summary of achievable positioning accuracy w.r.t. mean absolute error and the 90-th percentile for different trajectories of the AGV using EKF, LSTM, and DNN approaches. The mean absolute error is computed as

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |(p_{x_i} - \hat{p}_{x_i}) + (p_{y_i} - \hat{p}_{y_i})| \quad (22)$$

Fig. 6(a) depicts the ground truth trajectory of Run 1 and the estimated trajectory using different data fusion and

positioning approaches. In particular, the Run 1 trajectory follows a loop with multiple turns, resulting in an acceleration and de-acceleration of AGV as it travels in the loop. In general, all the positioning approaches estimate the trajectory of the AGV close to the ground truth. The data-driven approaches, namely LSTM and DNN, have smoother curves than EKF, especially at the turns. In addition, our proposed DNN-based data fusion and positioning solution reduces the positioning errors over a continuous path, achieving positioning results close to the ground truth compared to other baselines. The Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of 2D positioning errors of Run 1 trajectory for the investigated approaches is illustrated in Fig. 6(b). Analyzing the plots, one can infer that our proposed DNN-based positioning approach could avoid positioning errors at higher percentiles. For instance, looking at the CDF curves, it can be noted that the 90-th percentile positioning with EKF, LSTM, and DNN achieves errors of 27.5 cm, 21.8 cm, and 15 cm, respectively. The performance of the positioning technique at higher percentiles is important because deploying an indoor positioning system requires high reliability to ensure the safety of industrial assets and people. In particular, positioning with DNN achieves 45% and 31% accuracy improvements compared to positioning with EKF and LSTM. Furthermore, the mean absolute errors achieved with EKF, LSTM, and DNN are 21 cm, 10.1 cm, and 5.3 cm, respectively.

The Run 2 trajectory follows a loop with the circular (alike) path. Fig. 7(a) depicts the ground truth trajectory of Run 2 and the estimated trajectory using different data fusion and positioning approaches. Similar to the positioning results of Run 1 trajectory, the data-driven approaches, namely LSTM and DNN, have smoother curves than EKF. Our proposed DNN-based data fusion and positioning solution reduces the positioning errors over a continuous path, achieving positioning results close to the ground truth compared to other

(a) Estimated trajectory of AGV using different positioning approaches.

(b) CDF of 2D positioning error.

FIGURE 7. Comparison of EKF, LSTM, and DNN-based data fusion and positioning approaches for Run 2 trajectory.

(a) Estimated trajectory of AGV using different positioning approaches.

(b) CDF of 2D positioning error.

FIGURE 8. Comparison of EKF, LSTM, and DNN-based data fusion and positioning approaches for Run 3 trajectory.

baselines. The CDF of 2D positioning errors of Run 2 trajectory for the investigated approaches is illustrated in Fig. 7(b). At the 90-th percentile, positioning with EKF, LSTM, and DNN achieves errors of 30 cm, 23 cm, and 18 cm, respectively. In particular, positioning with DNN achieves 40% and 21% accuracy improvements compared to positioning with EKF and LSTM. Furthermore, the mean absolute errors achieved with EKF, LSTM, and DNN are 22.8, 14.2, and 7.6, respectively.

Lastly, the Run 3 follows an irregular path involving multiple turns. Fig. 8(a) depicts the ground truth trajectory of Run 3 and the estimated trajectory using different data fusion and

positioning approaches. The efficiency of our proposed DNN-based positioning approach can also be witnessed across the Run 3 trajectory, achieving positioning results close to the ground truth in comparison to other baselines. The CDF of 2D positioning errors of Run 3 trajectory for the investigated approaches is illustrated in Fig. 8(b). At the 90-th percentile, positioning with EKF, LSTM, and DNN achieves errors of 25.8 cm, 19.8 cm, and 16.2 cm, respectively. In particular, positioning with DNN achieves 37% and 18% accuracy improvements compared to positioning with EKF and LSTM. Furthermore, the mean absolute errors achieved with EKF, LSTM, and DNN are 15.5, 10, and 6.5, respectively.

TABLE 2. Comparison of Average Runtime for Different Trajectories of AGV Using EKF, LSTM, and DNN in Seconds (s)

Positioning solution	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3
EKF	0.012	0.007	0.012
Cascaded LSTM	0.260	0.273	0.300
Cascaded DNN	0.113	0.115	0.125

D. COMPARISON OF COMPUTATIONAL RUNTIME

We evaluate the runtime to obtain the position estimates of the AGV using each of the investigated algorithms across different trajectories. To this end, Table 2 shows each algorithm's average time in seconds (s). We implemented the algorithms in Python and executed them on a Linux machine of 13th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-i3850HX CPU, having a total of 20 cores with a memory of 30 GB. For data-driven positioning approaches like LSTM and DNN, only the time taken to obtain the position estimates during the execution or testing phase was reported. The training time was not included in the results. From the runtime results, we notice that LSTM runs slower and takes more time to compute the position estimates than EKF and DNN. In particular, EKF runs about $20\times$ faster than LSTM. Moreover, DNN runs about $3\times$ faster than LSTM. On the other hand, the runtime comparison between EKF and DNN shows that EKF runs about $9\times$ faster than DNN.

VI. DISCUSSION

We have experimentally evaluated the potential of EKF, LSTM, and DNN-based (proposed) positioning algorithms in achieving precise positioning accuracy of AGV in the indoor industrial scenario by fusing the measurements from UWB and IMU sensors. From our analysis, it can be concluded that the cascaded DNNs outperform the considered baselines, proving the proposed method's effectiveness in real-world industrial scenarios.

The superior performance of DNN over EKF in positioning the AGV is evident for the following reasons: (i) DNNs can be trained end-to-end with ground truth labels consisting of multiple processing chains merged into a single model. From training, the DNNs learn to minimize positional errors. In contrast, EKF requires separate models for predicting and updating the state vector or positional parameters. (ii) The training data allows the DNN to learn the underlying system dynamics and the non-linear relationships. On the other hand, the EKF requires the system dynamics to be modeled correctly. Furthermore, its performance is limited in linearizing the non-linear system through approximations. If the system dynamics are not modeled adequately, the EKF estimates can lead to noise spikes in the trajectory. (iii) DNNs are inherently designed to adapt to different types of perturbation in the training dataset. On the contrary, EKF assumes the noise model to be Gaussian and deviates from the actual performance if the assumption does not hold. Regarding runtime, EKF takes a shorter time to provide the position estimates than DNN. Although DNN takes a longer runtime, its improved performance justifies the increased runtime as it directly contributes

to reducing positioning errors and expanding the system's reliability in the industrial scenario. In addition, the runtime limitation of DNN can be avoided by using performance enhancements such as hardware accelerators and General Processing Units (GPUs).

Considering DNN and LSTM networks, it is observed that positioning with DNN achieves better results than LSTM. It is to be noted that, for the LSTM network, we used the data sequence length of 2, representing the measurements in two consecutive timesteps as inputs to the network to provide the position estimations. By increasing the data sequence length, it is possible to reduce the positioning errors with LSTM. However, increasing the data sequence length also increases the processing time to obtain the positioning results. This is proved numerically through the computational runtime tests, where LSTM takes longer to provide the position estimations. On the other hand, to enable the temporal prediction capability with our proposed DNN-based positioning approach, we have used the previous position of the AGV as an input to the network. Through this addition, we achieved better positioning results with shorter runtime than LSTM.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this paper, we have studied using DNNs as a data fusion and positioning solution in indoor industrial scenarios. Our study was carried out by considering an experimental setup of UWB and fusing its measurements with the IMU sensor to position the target AGV. The proposed DNN-based positioning solution is validated against the baselines EKF and LSTM regarding achievable positioning accuracy and the runtime for obtaining the position estimates. We consider different trajectories of the AGV to present the results of our analysis. The experimental results across all the investigated trajectories of AGV show that positioning with DNN outperforms EKF. In addition, the comparison between DNN and LSTM shows that integrating temporal capability into our proposed DNN-based positioning approach has provided accurate position estimates at shorter runtime than the LSTM approach. To this end, our proposed DNN-based positioning solution provides accurate position estimates, achieving a mean absolute error of less than 10 cm in the given industrial scenario.

Even though our proposed data fusion and positioning solution achieves good performance, it has a specific drawback. To work efficiently, our proposed DNN-based positioning solution expects the same number of inputs it has been trained for and cannot adapt to changes in the number of inputs. For instance, the AGV traversing in a large-scale multipath-dominant industrial scenario might not receive the positional information from all the anchors throughout its trajectory due to varying LoS/NLoS links. In such a case, our proposed approach might not yield optimal results. The positioning solution should be able to provide position estimates even under a varying number of inputs. We identify a few approaches to overcome this drawback. The first approach could be to train several neural networks, each with a specific number of inputs, and depending on the number of inputs received during run time, select the correct neural network to provide

the position estimations. The second approach could be to study the applicability of graph-based learning, such as Graph Neural Networks, which can adapt to varying numbers of inputs during runtime to solve the drawbacks mentioned. Furthermore, we also opine that our approach can be extended to other wireless infrastructures such as 5G and 6G Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) systems, which can provide measurements similar to UWB system based on timing approaches. Hence, future work includes studying and analyzing these approaches in industrial environments.

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